

target CRM	Cu	Cu	Cu	Ga	Eu, Y	Eu, Y	Sc	Sb	Al	Al	Mg	Mg	Sb	Si	Ga			
application/waste flow	external cables	internal cables and wiring	coils in motors	LEDs for general lighting and background illumination	LEDs for general lighting and background illumination	phosphor powder in fluorescent lamps (FLs) for general lighting and background illumination (CFLs)	incineration or energy recovery of plastic parts, flame retardants often volatilize or remain in residues/IV ash	heat sinks in various applications	Al alloys in casing, frame, chassis	alloying element in Al alloys in casing, frame, chassis	Mg alloys - mostly in casing	Mg alloys - mostly in casing	glass (e.g. LCD, CRT, solar)	silicon PV cells	thin layer in CIGS PV cells			
End treatment scenario without CRM recovery	mechanical treatment of devices, cables end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete liberation and separation, Cu ends up in landfill, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	mechanical treatment of devices, cables and wiring end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete liberation and separation, Cu ends up in landfill, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	mechanical treatment of devices, coils end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete liberation and separation, Cu ends up in landfill, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	fate of LED relevant, can either end up in plastics fraction or metal fraction, Ga ends up in bottom ash after incineration or smelter slag	fate of LED relevant, can either end up in plastics fraction or metal fraction, Eu and Y end up in bottom ash after incineration or smelter slag	due to their mercury content FLs need to be collected and treated separately, phosphor powder needs to be removed and is separated due to its Hg content, Mg is recovered through vaporisation, Eu and Y are not recovered	due to their mercury content metal halide lamps need to be collected and treated separately, Hg is recovered through vaporisation, Sc is not recovered	incineration or energy recovery of plastic parts, flame retardants often volatilize or remain in residues/IV ash	heat sinks mounted to components do not get separated and are shredded without complete liberation, Al alloys end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fractions	casing, frame, chassis do not get separated, entire device gets shredded without complete liberation, Al alloys end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fractions	Mg can also be an impurity in Al alloys after remelting if not functionally recycled or removed through demagging	Casing, frame, chassis do not get separated, entire device is shredded with or without complete liberation, Mg alloys end up in Al fraction, Mg oxidises easily at high temperatures, especially when not protected, MgO ends up in slag	antimony-containing glass is separated, but not recycled LCD glass and CRT after landfilled solar is recycled	PV panels are separate collected and receive treatment to recover Al, glass and silver, Si ends up in residue for waste incineration or landfill	this layer is either landfilled with residues from PV panel recycling or ends up in recycling fractions without an and Ga recovery			
(Partially) existing or potential End treatment scenario with CRM recovery	external cables are separated prior shredding, cable scrap undergoes a dedicated treatment with liberation, separation of insulation by density separation, and purification of liberated metals with magnetic separation, purified Cu with 95% purity goes to Cu remelting (Lobbi & Espinosa, 2022)	cables and wiring are separated prior shredding or end up in Cu-rich fraction for Cu remelting or secondary Cu refining - depending on quality (Lobbi & Espinosa, 2022)	coils are separated prior shredding, or hand separated from magnetic fraction, separated coils can be shredded and separated into a magnetic Fe fraction and Cu, the latter goes to Cu remelting or secondary Cu refining - depending on quality	selective removal of LED chips and subsequent thermal and hydrometallurgical treatment (Leberschauer, 2017b)	enrichment of REE possible with selective removal of LED chips and subsequent treatment, potentially Eu and Y can be by-product with Ga recovery from LED (Batter et al., 2016)	FLs are collected separately, phosphor powder needs to be removed and is separated due to its Hg content, Eu and Y can be recovered in a subsequent hydrometallurgical or combined pyro-hydrometallurgical process (Dhawan & Tanwar, 2022; European Commission, 2016; Niu et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2013; Figueiredo et al., 2025)	unlikely scenario, Sc is not recovered from metal halide lamps (Buteba et al., 2021; SCIREN CRM's fact sheets, 2023)	sorting of plastics according to bromine content into bromine flame retardant (BFR) containing and BFR-free plastics, or alternatively denser separation, plastic fraction with BFR can be chemically treated, there are different chemical recycling methods for Sb (Klassall et al., 2019; Gaudin et al., 2025; Spoonen, 2025)	selective removal of Al parts from the devices and separate collection after the first removal step or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation (sink/float separation, XRT, LIBS, XRF) from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze, sorted scrap for remelting of Al (Diaz-Romero et al., 2023; Park et al., 2020)	selective removal of Al parts from the devices and separate collection after the first removal step or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation (sink/float separation, XRT, LIBS, XRF) from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze, sorted scrap for remelting of Al (Diaz-Romero et al., 2023; Park et al., 2020)	selective removal of Al parts from the devices and separate collection after the first removal step or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation (sink/float separation, XRT, LIBS, XRF) from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze, sorted scrap for remelting of Al (Diaz-Romero et al., 2023; Park et al., 2020)	removal of magnesium alloy parts from the devices and separate collection followed by remelting or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze and Al alloys, sorted scrap may need removal of coating, remelting of Mg, if quality requires including refining (Wang et al., 2024)	antimony-containing glass is recycled in specialized facilities as antimony can lead to unwanted emissions and lower quality in standard recycling systems for glass (Solar Waste Solutions, n.d.)	PV panels are separate collected and receive treatment to recover Al, glass and silver, Si fraction is separated and purified after pyrolytic separation (Prest & Smith, 2024)	CIGS PV panels are collected separately, thin layers in the CIGS PV panels are separated with mechanical or thermal processing, followed by a hydrometallurgical or pyrometallurgical process to recover Ga (European Commission, 2016; X. Li et al., 2023)			
Nb. Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?																	
design/output-specific criteria																		
1.1 Disposition and heterogeneity in product/waste flow (accumulation and mass fraction within a product/waste flow)	How dispersed is the CRM and/or the CRM containing application in the product? Is the CRM and/or CRM containing application accumulated in specific components? Is the CRM accumulated/enriched in parts of the waste flow or is it more widely distributed within the waste flow? How is the CRM mass fraction in relation to the ore grade (in the application/component/product/parts of the waste flow)?	Cu is usually accumulated in specific components of which cables and wirings are the most common ones.	Cu is usually accumulated in specific components of which cables and wirings are the most common ones.	Cu is usually accumulated in specific components of which cables and wirings are the most common ones.	Ga is part of the LED chip, the chip is mainly made of group III-V compounds, such as gallium arsenide (GaAs), gallium nitride (GaN), indium gallium nitride (InGaN), and other semiconductors. The mass fraction of Ga in LED lamps is around 0.084-0.38% (Mir et al., 2023).	LED phosphors contain 0.006-0.1 g/bulb Y and 0.000-0.002 g/bulb Eu (Ku et al., 2015).	The phosphor used for luminescence behaviour makes up to 2-98% of FLs and consists of 9 to 26% REE content, significantly higher than the REE ore deposits (Dhawan & Tanwar, 2022).	FLs phosphors contain 0.34-0.75 g/bulb Y and 0.02-0.04 g/bulb Eu (Ku et al., 2015).	The inner arc tube in metal halide lamps houses a mixture of gases, typically including mercury and halides such as sodium or scandium, which are critical for producing light (PatLight, 2025).	Sb is encountered in plastics in a range that spans several orders of magnitude from the detection limit of a few tens of mg/kg to about 20wt% (Fialla et al., 2020).	Heat sinks can be found in various applications (machines, laptops, computers, routers, PCBs). Heat sinks are most often made of Al, sometimes Cu.	For heat sinks, mainly Al1050, 6060, 8061 or 6063 is used (Ye, 2021).	Al alloys are a typical material for casings, frames and chassis. Besides also Mg alloys and plastics are used widely.	Al-Mg alloys (5000e series) are mainly used when high corrosion resistance is required.	Mg alloys are a typical material for casings, frames and chassis. Besides also Al alloys and plastics are used widely.	Sb is only used in special glass types, in CRT glass, LCD glass and solar glass.	Silicon PV panels contain around 3-4% Si concentrated in the solar cells where the mass fraction is around 64% (Chen et al., 2024).	CIGS PV cells contain around 0.68% In and 0.24% Ga. These elements are concentrated in a thin layer on glass or plastic backing (Huang et al., 2024).
1.2 Change in product design/output (changes in quantities, replacements, etc.)	What are the current developments regarding change in product design, especially change in CRM quantities and replacements? Are there expected input changes that will affect the waste flow?	Design increasingly aims at standardized cable assemblies. However, cheaper cables are starting to contain more Al instead of Cu - difficult to separate out.	Cheaper cables are starting to contain more Al instead of Cu - difficult to separate out.	Cheaper cables are starting to contain more Al instead of Cu - difficult to separate out.	LEDs are taking over the illumination market (Ku et al., 2015).	LEDs are taking over the illumination market. While LED phosphors also use yttrium and europium, the quantities required are one to two orders of magnitude lower than what is needed to produce an equivalent amount of light using fluorescent bulbs (Ku et al., 2015).	LEDs are taking over the illumination market. While LED phosphors also use yttrium and europium, the quantities required are one to two orders of magnitude lower than what is needed to produce an equivalent amount of light using fluorescent bulbs (Ku et al., 2015).	No information	The flame retardant market incl. ATO and zinc borate is projected to grow due to higher fire safety standards and growth in the EEE and construction sector (Sati, 2025; Allied Market Research, 2025).	Not expected	Not expected	Not expected	Not expected	CRT monitors are phasing out.	Standardized products, the Si content in PV cells has decreased over the last years, silicon PV cells are still the dominating technology	Not expected		
1.3 Product information and labelling (identifiability of CRM containing applications and components)	Does the product labelling provide sufficient information about the mass fraction and location of CRM in the product? Is there a required or voluntary labelling?	No labelling currently. DPPs are required for energy-related products with eco-design requirements, information and communication technology products & other electronics (Stretton & Buzeti, 2024, ESPR, 2024). Additional regulations will follow.	No labelling currently. DPPs are required for energy-related products with eco-design requirements, information and communication technology products & other electronics (Stretton & Buzeti, 2024, ESPR, 2024). Additional regulations will follow.	No labelling currently. DPPs are required for energy-related products with eco-design requirements, information and communication technology products & other electronics (Stretton & Buzeti, 2024, ESPR, 2024). Additional regulations will follow.	Labels on lamps only contain information on lamp, Watt, Voltage, Hertz, and Kelvin and Hg content.	Labels on lamps only contain information on lamp, Watt, Voltage, Hertz, and Kelvin and Hg content.	Labels on lamps only contain information on lamp, Watt, Voltage, Hertz, and Kelvin and Hg content.	Labels on lamps only contain information on lamp, Watt, Voltage, Hertz, and Kelvin and Hg content.	DPPs are required for energy-related products with eco-design requirements, information and communication technology products & other electronics (Stretton & Buzeti, 2024, ESPR, 2024). Additional regulations will follow. According to the Classification, Labelling and Packaging regulation, waste is hazardous through the suspected carcinogenic properties of Sb. If the concentration of ATO is >0.1% (equivalent to a concentration of Sb of > 0.08 %) (Fialla et al., 2020; CLP-Regulation (EC) 1272/2008).	No labelling currently. DPPs are required for energy-related products with eco-design requirements, information and communication technology products & other electronics (Stretton & Buzeti, 2024, ESPR, 2024). Additional regulations will follow.	No labelling currently. DPPs are required for energy-related products with eco-design requirements, information and communication technology products & other electronics (Stretton & Buzeti, 2024, ESPR, 2024). Additional regulations will follow.	No labelling currently. DPPs are required for energy-related products with eco-design requirements, information and communication technology products & other electronics (Stretton & Buzeti, 2024, ESPR, 2024). Additional regulations will follow.	No labelling currently. DPPs are required for energy-related products with eco-design requirements, information and communication technology products & other electronics (Stretton & Buzeti, 2024, ESPR, 2024). Additional regulations will follow.	Some monitors are labelled. DPPs are required for energy-related products with eco-design requirements, information and communication technology products & other electronics (Stretton & Buzeti, 2024). Additional regulations will follow.	PV panels are labelled (model information). The PV panel type is known. DPPs are required for energy-related products with eco-design requirements, information and communication technology products & other electronics (Stretton & Buzeti, 2024). Additional regulations will follow.	PV panels are labelled (model information). The PV panel type is known. DPPs are required for energy-related products with eco-design requirements, information and communication technology products & other electronics (Stretton & Buzeti, 2024). Additional regulations will follow.		
waste flow-specific criteria																		
2.1 Disposition in waste flow	How high is the mass fraction of the CRM in the (collected) waste flow (in relation to the ore grade)? How is the CRM containing application collected (e.g. application-, component-, product-level, mixed with other products)? Is there a pre-sorting regarding input material/parts of the waste flow?	External cables are usually removed from the devices and collected as separate waste flow.	Internal cables and wiring are usually not dismantled from the devices.	Motors are sometimes removed from devices, but coils are not disassembled.	Lamps (except of incandescent) are collected separately. For background illumination, it depends on the product/device.	Lamps (except of incandescent) are collected separately. For background illumination, it depends on the product/device.	Lamps (except of incandescent) are collected separately. For background illumination, it depends on the product/device.	Lamps (except of incandescent) are collected separately.	Sb is not added to all plastic casings, only if the electronic product generates heat and flame retardants are required. Sb was detected in about 15% of several thousand consumer items analysed, and was most abundantly encountered in electrical equipment and items of (polyester) clothing (Fialla et al., 2020).	Heat sinks are often manually removed during disassembly.	Casing are sometimes dismantled depending on the device. Not all casings, frames and chassis are made out of Al alloys. Also, Mg alloys and plastics are frequently used.	Casing are sometimes dismantled depending on the device. Not all casings, frames and chassis are made out of Al alloys. Also, Al alloys and plastics are frequently used.	Casing are sometimes dismantled depending on the device. Not all casings, frames and chassis are made out of Mg alloys. Also, Al alloys and plastics are frequently used.	CRT monitors are collected separately. PV panels follow an own collection scheme. LCD displays are sometimes dismantled. Not all LCD displays and solar glass contain Sb.	PV panels are collected separately, high mass fraction of Si/PV cells in PV collection category.	PV panels are collected separately.		
2.2 Mineralogical state	In which mineralogical state is the CRM in the application or waste flow (e.g. metal, oxide, etc.)?	Native metal	Native metal	Native metal	Gallium arsenide or gallium nitride	phosphor powder	phosphor powder	Sodium-scandium-halide	Antimony trioxide (ATO)	Metal alloy	Metal alloy	Metal alloy	Metal alloy	CRT: Sb in glass LCD: Sb in indium tin oxide (ITO) glass layer Solar glass: Sb in solar glass	Si metal mono- or poly-crystalline (amorphous not relevant anymore)	Cu indium gallium arsenide		
2.3 Product and/or component collection (collection and return rates)	How high are the collection and return rates? Why are they high/low?	Can be missing and stolen for the value due to accessibility	Internal wiring is unlikely to be stolen for its value due to difficulty accessing it so collection rate will be as high as product collection.	Internal wiring is unlikely to be stolen for its value due to difficulty accessing it so collection rate will be as high as product collection.	Collection rate for lighting equipment in 2022 was 44% (WEEE collected/WEEE generated).	Collection rate for lighting equipment in 2022 was 44% (WEEE collected/WEEE generated).	Collection rate for lighting equipment in 2022 was 44% (WEEE collected/WEEE generated).	Collection rate for lighting equipment in 2022 was 44% (WEEE collected/WEEE generated).	Flame retardants can be found in EEE from all categories. The average collection rate of WEEE generated was calculated with 54% in the EU in 2021 and related to EEE POM with 44%. Reasons for the low collection rates are hoarding and losses in MSW (Baldé et al., 2022).	No information	Al alloys can be found in EEE from all categories. The average collection rate of WEEE related to WEEE generated was calculated with 54% in the EU in 2021 and related to EEE POM with 44%. Reasons for the low collection rates are hoarding and losses in MSW (Baldé et al., 2022).	Al alloys can be found in EEE from all categories. The average collection rate of WEEE related to WEEE generated was calculated with 54% in the EU in 2021 and related to EEE POM with 44%. Reasons for the low collection rates are hoarding and losses in MSW (Baldé et al., 2022).	Mg alloys can be found in EEE from all categories. The average collection rate of WEEE related to WEEE generated was calculated with 54% in the EU in 2021 and related to EEE POM with 44%. Reasons for the low collection rates are hoarding and losses in MSW (Baldé et al., 2022).	Depends on the product, high for PV panels	Collection of PV panels follows an own collection scheme. Collection rates are quite low, but this is also attributed to the calculation method.	Collection of PV panels follows an own collection scheme. Collection rates are quite low, but this is also attributed to the calculation method.		
2.4 Current waste generated	Which waste quantities are currently generated?	Most EEE has external cables, making it an easy accessible waste flow. Al cables usage is increasing.	No information	No information	LED already make up the biggest share in energy efficient lighting market (IBV Research, 2022).	LED already make up the biggest share in energy efficient lighting market (IBV Research, 2022).	The market share of FLs is decreasing but still a large share of waste lamps are FLs.	High-intensity discharge lamps (HID) where metal halide lamps are counted to have a similar market share as FLs (IBV Research, 2022).	No information	No information	Al alloys constitute a large proportion of casings, frames and chassis in EEE.	No information	No information	CRT monitors are phasing out. CRT waste generated is decreasing. LCD have the highest market share among all display types (Research Dive, 2023). Solar panels are a huge waste stream.	Currently <1% of WEEE collected, but rapid increase to be expected, silicon technology had a market share of around 82% in 2020 (IRENA, 2016)	Currently <1% of WEEE collected, but rapid increase to be expected. CIGS technology had a market share of around 5% in 2020 (IRENA, 2016)		

target CRM application/waste flow	Cu external cables	Cu internal cables and wiring	Cu coils in motors	Ga LEDs for general lighting and background illumination	Eu, Y LEDs for general lighting and background illumination	Eu, Y phosphor powder in fluorescent lamps (FLs) for general lighting and background illumination (CFLs)	Sc arc tube in metal halide lamps in camera or industrial and street lighting	Sb flame retardant in plastic casing	Al heat sinks in various applications	Al Al alloys in casing, frame, chassis	Mg alloying element in Al alloys in casing, frame, chassis	Mg Mg alloys - mostly in casing	Sb glass (e.g. LCD, CRT, solar)	Si silicon PV cells	Ga thin layer in CIGS PV cells
EoL treatment scenario without CRM recovery	mechanical treatment of devices, cables end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete liberation and separation. Cu ends up in landfill, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	mechanical treatment of devices, cables and wiring end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete liberation and separation. Cu ends up in landfill, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	mechanical treatment of devices, coils end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete liberation and separation. Cu ends up in landfill, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	fate of LED relevant, can either end up in plastics fraction or metal fraction. Ga ends up in bottom ash after incineration or smelter slag	fate of LED relevant, can either end up in plastics fraction or metal fraction. Eu and Y end up in bottom ash after incineration or smelter slag	due to their mercury content FLs need to be collected and treated separately, phosphor powder needs to be removed and is separated due to its Hg content. Eu and Y are not recovered	due to their mercury content metal halide lamps need to be collected and treated separately. Hg is recovered through vaporization. Sc is not recovered	incineration or energy recovery of plastic parts, flame retardants often volatilize or remain in residues/fly ash	heat sinks mounted to components do not get separated and are shredded without complete liberation. Al alloys end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fractions	casing, frame, chassis do not get separated, entire device gets shredded without complete liberation. Al alloys end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fractions	mechanical treatment of devices, Al alloys end up in wrong output fractions due to incomplete separation	Casing, frame, chassis do not get separated, entire device is shredded with or without complete liberation. Mg alloys end up in Al fraction. Mg solidifies easily at high temperature, especially when not protected. MgO ends up in slag	antimony-containing glass is separated, but not recycled. LCD glass and CRT often landfilled. Solar is recycled	PV panels are separate collected and receive treatment to recover Al, glass and silver. Si ends up in residue for waste incineration or landfill	this layer is either landfilled with residues from PV panel recycling or ends up in recycling fractions without in and Ga recovery
(Partially) existing or potential EoL treatment scenario with CRM recovery	external cables are separated prior shredding, cable scrap undergoes a dedicated treatment with liberation, separation of insulation by density separation, and purification of liberated metals with magnetic separation, purified Cu with 95% purity goes to Cu remelting (Lohb & Espinosa, 2021)	cables and wiring are separated prior shredding or end up in Cu rich fraction for Cu remelting or secondary Cu refining - depending on quality (Lohb & Espinosa, 2021)	coils are separated prior shredding, or hand separated from magnetic fraction, separated coils can be shredded and separated into a magnetic Fe fraction and Cu, the latter goes to Cu remelting or secondary Cu refining - depending on quality	selective removal of LED chips and subsequent thermal and hydrometallurgical treatment (Kebenschar, 2017b)	enrichment of REE possible with selective removal of LED chips and subsequent treatment, potentially Eu and Y can be by-product with Ga recovery from LED (Bhat et al., 2016)	FLs are collected separately, phosphor powder needs to be removed and is separated due to its Hg content. Eu and Y can be recovered in a subsequent hydrometallurgical process (Dhawan & Tanwar, 2022; European Commission, 2016; Niu et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2013; Figueiredo et al., 2025)	unlikely scenario, Sc is not recovered from metal halide lamps (Botelho et al., 2021; SCREEN CRMs fact sheets, 2023)	sorting of plastics according to bromine content into bromine flame retardant (BFR)-containing and BFR-free plastics or alternatively density separation, plastic fraction with BFR can be chemically treated, there are different chemical recycling methods for Sb (Massali et al., 2019; Gaudin et al., 2023; Spoonen, 2025)	selective removal of Al parts from the devices and separate collection after the first removal step or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation (sink/float separation, XRT, LIBS, XRF) from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze, sorted scrap for remelting of Al (Diaz-Romero et al., 2023; Park et al., 2021)	selective removal of Al parts from the devices and separate collection after the first removal step or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation (sink/float separation, XRT, LIBS, XRF) from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze, sorted scrap for remelting of Al (Diaz-Romero et al., 2023; Park et al., 2021)	selective removal of Al parts from the devices and separate collection after the first removal step or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation (sink/float separation, XRT, LIBS, XRF) from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze, sorted scrap further separated into 5000 and 6000 series Al scrap with LIBS allowing functional Mg recovery and preventing demagging (Diaz-Romero et al., 2023; Park et al., 2021)	removal of magnesium alloy parts from the devices and separate collection followed by remelting or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze and Al alloys, sorted scrap may need removal of coating, refining of Mg, if quality requires including remelting (Wang et al., 2024)	antimony-containing glass is recycled in specialized facilities as antimony can lead to unwanted emissions and lower quality in standard recycling systems for glass (Solar Waste Solutions, n.d.)	PV panels are separate collected and receive treatment to recover Al, glass and silver. Si fraction is separated and purified after pyrolytic separation (Prest & Smith, 2014)	CIGS PV panels are collected separately, the layers in the CIGS PV panels are separated with mechanical or thermal processing followed by a hydrometallurgical or pyrometallurgical process to recover Ga (European Commission, 2016; X. Li et al., 2023)
Nb. Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?														
2.5 Future waste generated	Which waste quantities are expected to be generated in the future?														
	Increased use of Al cables.	Increased use of Al cables.	Increased use of Al cables.	The market share of LEDs will increase.	The market share of LEDs will increase.	The market share of FLs is decreasing.	The metal halide lamps market is expected to grow (Raje, 2023).	No information	No information	Al alloys constitute a large proportion of casings, frames and chassis in EEE which might increase more according to recyclers (especially for frames).	No information	No information	CRT waste generated will further decrease.	Strong increase, largest share in WEEE generated in 2050, currently approx. 20% of POM. Market share of silicon PV technology might decline to 70% in 2030 (IRENA, 2016).	Strong increase, largest share in WEEE generated in 2050, currently approx. 20% of POM. Market share of thin film PV panels (incl. CdTe) is projected to grow (Dhawan Chowdhury et al., 2020), 4% in 2030 (IRENA, 2016).
3.1 Availability of identification technology for CRM containing application/material/component/product	Is there a technology to identify the CRM containing application/component/product to enable its recovery?														
	In most cases Cu can be identified visually due to its colour or based on its application, e.g. cables, coils.	In most cases Cu can be identified visually due to its colour or based on its application, e.g. cables, coils.	In most cases Cu can be identified visually due to its colour or based on its application, e.g. cables, coils.	LED chips can be identified visually.	The phosphor powder is on the LED chips which can be identified visually.	Not needed, Eu and Y are in the phosphor powder.	The arc tube can be identified visually.	Sb detection with energy-dispersive portable XRF technology. Specifically, a Niton XL3t instrument has been deployed in situ or in an accessory stand using a low density plastics mode and with appropriate thickness correction (Fialla et al., 2020).	Heat sinks can be identified visually. LIBS and XRF technology can detect composition or Al series. However, XRF cannot detect light elements, like Li, Si, etc., so it is mainly used for Cu-containing alloys.	In many cases Al can be identified visually. LIBS and XRF technology can detect composition or Al series. However, XRF cannot detect light elements, like Li, Si, etc., so it is mainly used for Cu-containing alloys.	In many cases Al can be identified visually. LIBS and XRF technology can detect composition or Al series. However, XRF cannot detect light elements, like Li, Si, etc., so it is mainly used for Cu-containing alloys.	Mg alloys often end up in the Al fraction as they are not easy to identify and separate from Al alloys. LIBS and XRF technology can detect composition. However, XRF cannot detect light elements, like Li, Si, etc., so it is mainly used for Cu-containing alloys.	All applications can be identified. Not all LCD displays and solar glass contain Sb. There is no rapid detection method known (ESIA, 2023).	Visual identification possible	The CIGS layer can be identified visually.
3.2 Manual removability of CRM containing application/material/component (selective removal)	Is it possible to manually remove the CRM containing application/component or material from the product/waste flow (is it screwed, glued, welded)?														
	External cables can be easily removed manually.	Internal cables and wiring are possible to remove manually, but labour-intensive.	It is possible to manually remove coils in motors.	It is possible to manually separate LED backlights during disassembly. Manual removal of LED chips from general lighting is not practised.	It is possible to manually separate LED backlights during disassembly. Manual removal of LED chips from general lighting is not practised.	Not possible	No	In many cases, it is possible to manually remove the casing from the products.	Simple manual removal during disassembly	Partially possible, requires unscrewing or breaking of casing.	Partially possible, requires unscrewing or breaking of casing.	Partially possible, requires unscrewing or breaking of casing.	CRT can be removed manually. LCD displays can be removed manually, but the ITO glass layer cannot be removed manually from the other layers. The solar glass can not be manually separated from other layers of the PV module (Prest & Smith, 2014)	No manual separation possible, thermal or chemical pre-treatment required	The CIGS layer can be removed by mechanical scraping (M. Li et al., 2023).
3.3 Automated removability of CRM containing application/material/component (selective removal)	Are processes available to remove the CRM containing application/component by automation? What is its TRL level?														
	External cables are usually removed manually before further treatment as they can block machinery. Cable sheathing can be removed in an automated way.	There is a lot of research and trials regarding semi-automated disassembly and intelligent disassembly of WEEE. However, 100% automation in WEEE disassembly without human assistance is still unfulfillable (Lu et al., 2023).	There is a lot of research and trials regarding semi-automated disassembly and intelligent disassembly of WEEE. However, 100% automation in WEEE disassembly without human assistance is still unfulfillable (Lu et al., 2023).	No technology known, but this is the crucial step. LED chips should be removed to create a fraction that concentrates In and Ga.	No technology known, but this is the crucial step. LED chips should be removed to create a fraction that concentrates Eu and Y.	Phosphor powder can be removed with the "end push method" where the end caps of FLs are cut off and the phosphor powder is pushed out using scraper, high-pressure air or water (Dhawan & Tanwar, 2022). In an interview with a recycling company, also Local Exhaust Ventilation (LEV) technology was mentioned as a method to remove phosphor powder.	No	There is a lot of research and trials regarding semi-automated disassembly and intelligent disassembly of WEEE. However, 100% automation in WEEE disassembly without human assistance is still unfulfillable (Lu et al., 2023).	No information	There is a lot of research and trials regarding semi-automated disassembly and intelligent disassembly of WEEE. However, 100% automation in WEEE disassembly without human assistance is still unfulfillable (Lu et al., 2023).	There is a lot of research and trials regarding semi-automated disassembly and intelligent disassembly of WEEE. However, 100% automation in WEEE disassembly without human assistance is still unfulfillable (Lu et al., 2023).	There is a lot of research and trials regarding semi-automated disassembly and intelligent disassembly of WEEE. However, 100% automation in WEEE disassembly without human assistance is still unfulfillable (Lu et al., 2023).	There is a lot of research and trials regarding semi-automated disassembly and intelligent disassembly of WEEE. However, 100% automation in WEEE disassembly without human assistance is still unfulfillable (Lu et al., 2023).	No automated separation possible, thermal or chemical pre-treatment required	The CIGS layer can be removed by mechanical scraping (M. Li et al., 2023).
3.4 Identifiability and separability of CRM containing material after liberation	Is it possible to identify and sort the CRM containing materials after liberation (e.g. shredding)? This can be without preceding removal/sorting or after preceding removal.														
	Non-ferrous metals can be separated with eddy current separation. The non-ferrous metal fraction can be further separated by density separation into a Cu and Al fraction.	Non-ferrous metals can be separated with eddy current separation. The non-ferrous metal fraction can be further separated by density separation into a Cu and Al fraction.	Non-ferrous metals can be separated with eddy current separation. The non-ferrous metal fraction can be further separated by density separation into a Cu and Al fraction.	Not possible	Not possible	Phosphor powder can also be removed after shredding whole FL with filters capturing the vapour and dust (Dhawan & Tanwar, 2022).	No information	Plastics can be sorted NIR technology and density separation.	Non-ferrous metals can be separated from a waste flow by eddy current separation. The non-ferrous metal fraction can be further separated by density separation or XRT sensor-based sorting into a Cu and Al fraction. Al scrap can be sorted according to alloy type or series with LIBS or other sensor-based sorting technologies. Sensor-based sorting technologies are limited to Al scrap with high mass fraction of alloying elements and low variability within the fractions that should be separated.	Non-ferrous metals can be separated from a waste flow by eddy current separation. The non-ferrous metal fraction can be further separated by density separation or XRT sensor-based sorting into a Cu and Al fraction. Al scrap can be sorted according to alloy type or series with LIBS or other sensor-based sorting technologies. Sensor-based sorting technologies are limited to Al scrap with high mass fraction of alloying elements and low variability within the fractions that should be separated.	Non-ferrous metals can be separated from a waste flow by eddy current separation. The non-ferrous metal fraction can be further separated by density separation or XRT sensor-based sorting into a Cu and Al fraction. Al scrap can be sorted according to alloy type or series with LIBS or other sensor-based sorting technologies. Sensor-based sorting technologies are limited to Al scrap with high mass fraction of alloying elements and low variability within the fractions that should be separated.	Non-ferrous metals can be separated from a waste flow by eddy current separation. The non-ferrous metal fraction can be further separated by density separation or XRT sensor-based sorting devices into a heavy- (Cu) and light-weight (Al and Mg) fraction. The light metals can be separated from each other through spectroscopic techniques to obtain a relatively pure Mg scrap flow suitable for melting (Wang et al., 2024)	CRT, LCD displays and solar glass should be removed before shredding to targeted recovery. Post-shredding glass sorting will not comply with quality requirements.	Thermal or chemical pre-treatment required prior separation, mechanical sorting applied for separating liberated Si pieces	Typically, the different layers in CIGS PV modules are separated with mechanical or thermal processing, the CIGS layer is scraped off. The CIGS layer is then crushed/grinded followed by leaching (pyrometallurgical process) (X. Li et al., 2023). CIGS can also be liberated only by crushing and grinding (M. Li et al., 2023).
3.5 Ability to concentrate CRM containing material / mechanically remove impurities	Is it possible to concentrate or to mechanically remove impurities from the CRM containing material flow?														
	Cables are separated from the main flow in a positive sorting process. Pure fractions such as cables can be remelted after the removal of insulation.	Cables are separated from the main flow in a positive sorting process. Pure fractions such as cables can be remelted after the removal of insulation.	Cu scrap is either collected separated at source or separated from other fractions after shredding in a positive sorting process. Pure fractions such as cables can be remelted after the removal of insulation. Further removal of impurities is of less relevance. Purity requirements of the input material for an integrated Cu smelter are low.	The LED chips need to be liberated in with mechanical, chemical and thermal pre-treatment steps (Mir et al., 2022).	No information	Due to shredding whole FL, glass particles can contaminate the captured phosphor powder which requires further treatment (Dhawan & Tanwar, 2022).	No information	There is no technology to sort plastics according to the used flame retardant types except the sorting of plastics according to their bromine content into bromine flame retardant (BFR)-containing and BFR-free plastics, combining XRT and NIR technology (Bonfazi et al., 2021; TOMRA Recycling, 2025).	Al scrap is separated from other fractions in a positive sorting process. Further removal of impurities is of less relevance. High quality requirements for positive sorting, losses in residues are taken into account to achieve quality requirements.	Al scrap is separated from other fractions in a positive sorting process. Further removal of impurities is of less relevance. High quality requirements for positive sorting, losses in residues are taken into account to achieve quality requirements.	Al scrap is separated from other fractions in a positive sorting process. Further removal of impurities is of less relevance. High quality requirements for positive sorting, losses in residues are taken into account to achieve quality requirements.	Mg scrap is separated from other fractions in a positive sorting process. Further removal of impurities is of less relevance. High quality requirements for positive sorting, losses in residues are taken into account to achieve quality requirements.	CRT, LCD displays and solar glass should be removed before shredding for targeted recovery. Post-shredding glass sorting will not comply with quality requirements.	Thermal or chemical pre-treatment required prior separation, mechanical sorting applied for separating liberated Si pieces	Not needed

target CRM application/waste flow	Cu external cables	Cu internal cables and wiring	Cu coils in motors	Ga LEDs for general lighting and background illumination	Eu, Y LEDs for general lighting and background illumination	Eu, Y phosphor powder in fluorescent lamps (FLs) for general lighting and background illumination (CFLs)	Sc arc tube in metal halide lamps in camera or industrial and street lighting	Sb flame retardant in plastic casing	Al heat sinks in various applications	Al Al alloys in casing, frame, chassis	Mg alloying element in Al alloys in casing, frame, chassis	Mg Mg alloys - mostly in casing	Sb glass (e.g. LCD, CRT, solar)	Si silicon PV cells	Ga thin layer in CIGS PV cells	
EoL treatment scenario without CRM recovery	mechanical treatment of devices, cables end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete liberation and separation, Cu ends up in landfill, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	mechanical treatment of devices, cables and wiring end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete liberation and separation, Cu ends up in landfill, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	mechanical treatment of devices, coils end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete separation, Cu ends up in landfill, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al induction motors may go directly to steel recycling where Cu is lost as impurity	fate of LED relevant, can either end up in plastics fraction or metal fraction, Ga ends up in bottom ash after incineration or smelter slag	fate of LED relevant, can either end up in plastics fraction or metal fraction, Eu and Y end up in bottom ash after incineration or smelter slag	due to their mercury content FLs need to be collected and treated separately, phosphor powder needs to be removed and is separated due to its Hg content, Mg is recovered through vaporization, Eu and Y are not recovered	due to their mercury content metal halide lamps need to be collected and treated separately, Mg is recovered through vaporization, Sc is not recovered	incineration or energy recovery of plastic parts, flame retardants often volatilize or remain in residues/fly ash	heat sinks mounted to components do not get separated and are shredded without complete liberation, Al alloys end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fractions	casing, frame, chassis do not get separated, entire device gets shredded without complete liberation, Al alloys end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fractions	mechanical treatment of devices, Al alloys end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete separation	Casing, frame, chassis do not get separated, entire device is shredded with or without complete liberation, Mg alloys end up in Al fraction, Mg solidifies easily at high temperature, especially when not protected, MgO ends up in slag	antimony-containing glass is separated, but not recycled LCD glass and CRT after landfilled solar is recycled	PV panels are separate collected and receive treatment to recover Al, glass and silver, Si ends up as residue for waste incineration or landfill	this layer is either landfilled with residues from PV panel recycling or ends up in recycling fractions without in and Ga recovery	
(Partially) existing or potential EoL treatment scenario with CRM recovery	external cables are separated prior shredding, cable scrap undergoes a dedicated treatment with liberation, separation of insulation by density separation, and purification of liberated metals with magnetic separation, purified Cu with 95% purity goes to Cu remelting (Lohli & Espinosa, 2021)	cables and wiring are separated prior shredding or end up in Cu rich fraction for Cu remelting or secondary Cu refining - depending on quality (Lohli & Espinosa, 2021)	coils are separated prior shredding, or hand separated from magnetic fraction, separated coils can be shredded and separated into a magnetic Fe fraction and Cu, the latter goes to Cu remelting or secondary Cu refining - depending on quality	selective removal of LED chips and subsequent thermal and hydrometallurgical treatment (Lieberman, 2017b)	enrichment of REE possible with selective removal of LED chips and subsequent treatment, potentially Eu and Y can be hydrolyzed with Ga recovery from LED (Bhatia et al., 2016)	FLs are collected separately, phosphor powder needs to be removed and is separated due to its Hg content, Eu and Y can be recovered in a subsequent hydrometallurgical or combined pyrometallurgical process (Dhawan & Tanwar, 2022; European Commission, 2016; Niu et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2013; Figueiredo et al., 2025)	unlikely scenario, Sc is not recovered from metal halide lamps (Bhatia et al., 2017; SCREEN CRMs fact sheets, 2023)	sorting of plastics according to bromine content into bromine flame retardant (BFR)-containing and BFR-free plastics or alternatively density separation, plastic fraction with BFR can be chemically treated, there are different chemical recycling methods for Sb (Alasali et al., 2019; Gaudin et al., 2025; Spooner, 2025)	selective removal of Al parts from the devices and separate collection after the first removal step or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation (sink/float separation, XRT, LIBS, XRF) from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze, sorted scrap for remelting of Al (Diaz-Romero et al., 2023; Park et al., 2021)	selective removal of Al parts from the devices and separate collection after the first removal step or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation (sink/float separation, XRT, LIBS, XRF) from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze, sorted scrap for remelting of Al (Diaz-Romero et al., 2023; Park et al., 2021)	selective removal of Al parts from the devices and separate collection after the first removal step or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation (sink/float separation, XRT, LIBS, XRF) from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze, sorted scrap for remelting of Al (Diaz-Romero et al., 2023; Park et al., 2021)	removal of magnesium alloy parts from the devices and separate collection followed by remelting or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze and Al alloys, sorted scrap may need removal of coating, remelting of Mg, if quality requires including refining (Wang et al., 2024)	antimony-containing glass is recycled in specialized facilities as antimony can lead to unwanted emissions and lower quality in standard recycling systems for glass (Solar Waste Solutions, n.d.)	PV panels are separate collected and receive treatment to recover Al, glass and silver, Si fraction is separated and purified after pyrolytic separation (Prest & Smith, 2024)	CIGS PV panels are collected separately, the layers in the CIGS PV panels are separated with mechanical or thermal processing followed by a hydrometallurgical or pyrometallurgical process to recover Ga (European Commission, 2016; X. Li et al., 2023)	
Nb. Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?															
3.6 Ability to thermally and/or chemically separate and refine CRMs from concentrates	Is there a thermal and/or chemical recovery technology for the CRM? What is its TRL level?	Cu cable scrap can be remelted.	Cu cable scrap can be remelted.	Pure Cu scrap can be remelted, more complex waste flows can be used as an input material in an integrated Cu smelter.	Selective recovery of Ga via hydrometallurgical extraction (leaching with NaOH, purification and electro-winning) is possible (European Commission, 2016; Flens et al., 2019)	No information	Eu and Y can be recovered in a hydrometallurgical or combined pyrometallurgical process from the extracted phosphor powder (Dhawan & Tanwar, 2022; European Commission, 2016; Niu et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2013)	No information	Currently, there is no recovery of Sb from plastics. However, there are a few studies on potential technologies, including solvometallurgical recovery and other extraction methods (Alasali et al., 2019; Gaudin et al., 2025; Spooner, 2025)	For functional recycling, purity requirements of the input material for remelting are high as the refining possibilities are limited. Mg as alloying element can be removed by different demagging processes (high energy and chemical input required). Most alloying elements remain in the metal phase, thus Al alloy needs to be diluted to achieve quality specification.	For functional recycling, purity requirements of the input material for remelting are high as the refining possibilities are limited. Mg as alloying element can be removed by different demagging processes (high energy and chemical input required). Most alloying elements remain in the metal phase, thus Al alloy needs to be diluted to achieve quality specification.	For functional recycling, purity requirements of the input material for remelting are high as the refining possibilities are limited. Mg as alloying element can be removed by different demagging processes (high energy and chemical input required). Most alloying elements remain in the metal phase, thus Al alloy needs to be diluted to achieve quality specification.	For functional recycling, purity requirements of the input material for remelting are high as the refining possibilities are limited. Mg as alloying element can be removed by different demagging processes (high energy and chemical input required). Most alloying elements remain in the metal phase, thus Al alloy needs to be diluted to achieve quality specification.	No information	e.g. ROSI SAS process (ROSI SAS, n.d.)	Different hydrometallurgical and pyrometallurgical technologies are available, purity requirements remain a challenge (X. Li et al., 2023).
economic criteria																
4.1 Market and quality of 2CRM	Is there a market for the 2CRM? What is the quality of the 2CRM compared to the primary one? How volatile is the market?	There is a Cu scrap market.	There is a Cu scrap market.	There is a Cu scrap market.	There is no market for removed LED backlights according to interviews with recyclers.	There is no market for removed LED backlights according to interviews with recyclers.	No information	No information	There is a market for secondary recycled plastics. Sb is widely dispersed in products derived from recycling (Fiala et al., 2020).	There is an Al scrap market. Oftentimes Al scrap is not sorted according to alloy type or series and can only be downcycled to cast Al or ends up as scrap surplus. Additionally, non-ferrous metal scrap which is a mix of Al, Cu and other alloys is traded and can be e.g. used as input material for an integrated Cu smelter where Al ends up in the slag.	There is an Al scrap market. Oftentimes Al scrap is not sorted according to alloy type or series and can only be downcycled to cast Al or ends up as scrap surplus. Additionally, non-ferrous metal scrap which is a mix of Al, Cu and other alloys is traded and can be e.g. used as input material for an integrated Cu smelter where Al ends up in the slag.	There is an Al scrap market. Oftentimes Al scrap is not sorted according to alloy type or series and can only be downcycled to cast Al or ends up as scrap surplus. Additionally, non-ferrous metal scrap which is a mix of Al, Cu and other alloys is traded and can be e.g. used as input material for an integrated Cu smelter where Al ends up in the slag.	There are different Mg scrap classes. However, most EoL Mg scrap is neither effectively recycled nor refined (Wang et al., 2024; Bell et al., 2017).	No, low price and limited interest	There is a market and demand for secondary Si	No information
4.2 Price competition of 2CRM with primary	Would it be cheaper to use the waste flow instead of an ore to recover the CRM?	There is no price difference between primary and secondary Cu.	There is no price difference between primary and secondary Cu.	There is no price difference between primary and secondary Cu.	No information	No information	There is no price difference between primary and secondary Eu and Y.	No information	Unclear, depends also on purity of sorted fractions, currently no recovery of Sb from plastics	The price for Al scrap depends on its quality and the demand for that quality on the market. There is no direct price competition between primary and secondary Al. Not every quality can be achieved with secondary Al.	The price for Al scrap depends on its quality and the demand for that quality on the market. There is no direct price competition between primary and secondary Al. Not every quality can be achieved with secondary Al.	The price for Al scrap depends on its quality and the demand for that quality on the market. There is no direct price competition between primary and secondary Al. Not every quality can be achieved with secondary Al.	The price for Mg scrap depends on its quality and the demand for that quality on the market. There is no direct price competition between primary and secondary Mg. Not every quality can be achieved with secondary Mg.	No information	Not competitive because of low value of Si compared to Ag and Cu and the lack of recycling uses (Gu et al., 2022; Diaz-Suarez et al., 2024; Komoto et al., 2022).	No information
4.3 Economic incentives	Do specific economic incentives exist (tax related, fees, etc.) to recover the CRM? Are there other materials or elements driving the recovery?	There are no economic incentives related to taxes or fees, but Cu is a valuable material.	There are no economic incentives related to taxes or fees, but Cu is a valuable material.	There are no economic incentives related to taxes or fees, but Cu is a valuable material.	No	No	No	No	No	Remelting Al needs significantly lower temperature and therefore energy than primary Al production. Therefore, emission trading and in the future the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) can act as an economic incentive for Al recycling.	Remelting Al needs significantly lower temperature and therefore energy than primary Al production. Therefore, emission trading and in the future the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) can act as an economic incentive for Al recycling.	Remelting Al needs significantly lower temperature and therefore energy than primary Al production. Therefore, emission trading and in the future the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) can act as an economic incentive for Al recycling.	Remelting Mg needs significantly lower temperature and therefore energy than primary Al production. Therefore, emission trading and in the future the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) can act as an economic incentive for Al recycling.	No	Si production has high energy demand, therefore, emission trading and in the future the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) can act as an economic incentive for recycling.	No
4.4 Economically viable case studies	Are there (potentially) economically viable case studies for the recovery of the CRM? Does the value or the quantity of the CRM play a decisive role?	There are many operating Cu smelters using clean Cu scrap. Integrated smelters can recover more complex waste flows, like PCBs, filter dust, or electronic components.	There are many operating Cu smelters using clean Cu scrap. Integrated smelters can recover more complex waste flows, like PCBs, filter dust, or electronic components.	There are many operating Cu smelters using clean Cu scrap. Integrated smelters can recover more complex waste flows, like PCBs, filter dust, or electronic components.	No information	No information	Different industrial applications (Dhawan & Tanwar, 2022).	No information	No	Applied in industrial scale	Applied in industrial scale	Applied in industrial scale	No information	No	Full scale plant from ROSI SAS (ROSI, n.d.)	LuChemie GmbH and Flavres provide technology to recover Ga from CIGS (FLAVRES, 2023; FLAVRES, 2025)
4.5 Recycling conflicts with other materials or elements (especially more valuable ones)	Is there a recycling conflict with other materials or elements, especially with more valuable ones in the product/waste flow?	There are no recycling conflicts with other materials or elements. Cu recycling is amplified as it is a carrier element for precious metal recovery. REE, Al, Mg, Fe, Ta, and other slag forming elements are typically lost.	There are no recycling conflicts with other materials or elements. Cu recycling is amplified as it is a carrier element for precious metal recovery. REE, Al, Mg, Fe, Ta, and other slag forming elements are typically lost.	There are no recycling conflicts with other materials or elements. Cu recycling is amplified as it is a carrier element for precious metal recovery. REE, Al, Mg, Fe, Ta, and other slag forming elements are typically lost.	Precious metals - comprise higher total masses and generate more revenues compared to In, Ga, an REE in LEDs (Nikubai et al., 2021).	Precious metals - comprise higher total masses and generate more revenues compared to In, Ga, an REE in LEDs (Nikubai et al., 2021).	No information	No information	Currently, the focus is on the recovery of the plastic, not the Sb.	Al in composite components with Cu. Separation is usually focusing on Cu, less on Al due to low tolerance to impurities.	Al in composite components with Cu. Separation is usually focusing on Cu, less on Al due to low tolerance to impurities.	Al in composite components with Cu. Separation is usually focusing on Cu, less on Al due to low tolerance to impurities.	Al when the light-weight metal fraction is not further sorted	CRT: no LCD. In Solar glass: focus on the glass	Not all PV recycling plants recover Si, Glass, Al and Ag, are core target materials, Si requires further purification steps.	No
environmental criteria																
5.1 Logistics and infrastructure	How are the logistic and infrastructure requirements for the recovery process (process steps, distances, etc.)? Can existing infrastructure be used?	There is an established infrastructure for Cu recycling, both direct remelting or integrated smelters for more complex waste flows.	There is an established infrastructure for Cu recycling, both direct remelting or integrated smelters for more complex waste flows.	There is an established infrastructure for Cu recycling, both direct remelting or integrated smelters for more complex waste flows.	Not existing	Not existing	Established infrastructure for removal of phosphor powders from FLs. Processing phosphor powder rich in REE is still evolving. (Dhawan & Tanwar, 2022).	Not existing	Not existing	There is an established infrastructure for Al recycling (sorting and remelting). LIBS is an emerging technology enabling higher quality recycling separating 5000 and 6000 series Al. To establish the necessary logistics, a minimum volume of Al scrap is needed.	There is an established infrastructure for Al recycling (sorting and remelting). LIBS is an emerging technology enabling higher quality recycling separating 5000 and 6000 series Al. To establish the necessary logistics, a minimum volume of Al scrap is needed.	There is an established infrastructure for Al recycling (sorting and remelting). LIBS is an emerging technology enabling higher quality recycling separating 5000 and 6000 series Al. To establish the necessary logistics, a minimum volume of Al scrap is needed.	No established infrastructure, most Mg scrap is neither effectively recycled nor utilized (Wang et al., 2024)	Not existing	Collection infrastructure exists, not all PV recycling plants recover Si.	Not existing
5.2 Energy and chemical requirements for separation and sorting	What are the energy and chemical requirements for mechanical separation and sorting?	Less sorting effort due to higher impurity tolerance of the melting process.	Less sorting effort due to higher impurity tolerance of the melting process.	Less sorting effort due to higher impurity tolerance of the melting process.	No information	No information	No information	No information	No information	Increased sensor-based sorting requires pressurized air and increases electricity demand (Ludwig et al., 2022). However, they are minimal compared to shredding (2kW for robotics and argons compared to 500kW for a shredder).	Increased sensor-based sorting requires pressurized air and increases electricity demand (Ludwig et al., 2022). However, they are minimal compared to shredding (2kW for robotics and argons compared to 500kW for a shredder).	Increased sensor-based sorting requires pressurized air and increases electricity demand (Ludwig et al., 2022). However, they are minimal compared to shredding (2kW for robotics and argons compared to 500kW for a shredder).	Increased sensor-based sorting requires pressurized air and increases electricity demand (Ludwig et al., 2022).	No information	Energy input for pyrolysis needed	No information
5.3 Energy and chemical requirements for thermal and/or chemical recovery	What are the energy and chemical requirements for thermal and/or (bio)chemical recovery in comparison with primary production?	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (saving up to 85% energy) (Asmatulu & Asmatulu, 2011; EuRic, n.d.).	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (saving up to 85% energy) (Asmatulu & Asmatulu, 2011; EuRic, n.d.).	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (saving up to 85% energy) (Asmatulu & Asmatulu, 2011; EuRic, n.d.).	No information	No information	High input of chemicals for processing necessary (Lieberman, 2017c).	No information	No information	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (saving up to 95% energy) (Asmatulu & Asmatulu, 2011; EuRic, n.d.).	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (saving up to 95% energy) (Asmatulu & Asmatulu, 2011; EuRic, n.d.).	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (saving up to 95% energy) (Asmatulu & Asmatulu, 2011; EuRic, n.d.).	Depends on the processing and purification requirements and technologies (Wang et al., 2024).	No information	Reduces energy demand relative to primary production (Rahi et al., 2023)	Requires different acids or alkaline solutions for leaching (X. Li et al., 2023)

target CRM application/waste flow	Cu external cables	Cu internal cables and wiring	Cu coils in motors	Ga LEDs for general lighting and background illumination	Eu, Y LEDs for general lighting and background illumination	Eu, Y phosphor powder in fluorescent lamps (FLs) for general lighting and background illumination (CFLs)	Sc arc tube in metal halide lamps in camera or industrial and street lighting	Sb flame retardant in plastic casing	Al heat sinks in various applications	Al Al alloys in casing, frame, chassis	Mg alloying element in Al alloys in casing, frame, chassis	Mg Mg alloys - mostly in casing	Sb glass (e.g. LCD, CRT, solar)	Si silicon PV cells	Ga thin layer in CIGS PV cells
EoL treatment scenario without CRM recovery	mechanical treatment of devices, cables end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete liberation and separation, Cu ends up in landfill, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	mechanical treatment of devices, cables and wiring end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete liberation and separation, Cu ends up in landfill, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	mechanical treatment of devices, coils end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete liberation and separation, Cu ends up in landfill, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	fate of LED relevant, can either end up in plastics fraction or metal fraction, Ga ends up in bottom ash after incineration or smelter slag	fate of LED relevant, can either end up in plastics fraction or metal fraction, Eu and Y end up in bottom ash after incineration or smelter slag	due to their mercury content FLs need to be collected and treated separately, phosphor powder needs to be removed and is separated due to its Hg content, Hg is recovered through vapourisation, Eu and Y are not recovered	due to their mercury content metal halide lamps need to be collected and treated separately, Hg is recovered through vapourisation, Sc is not recovered	incineration or energy recovery of plastic parts, flame retardants often volatilize or remain in residues/fly ash	heat sinks mounted to components do not get separated and are shredded without complete liberation, Al alloys end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fractions	casing, frame, chassis do not get separated, entire device gets shredded without complete liberation, Al alloys end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fractions	mechanical treatment of devices, Al alloys end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fractions	Casing, frame, chassis do not get separated, entire device is shredded with or without complete liberation, Mg alloys end up in Al fraction, Mg oxidizes easily at high temperatures, especially when not protected, MgO ends up in slag	antimony-containing glass is separated, but not recycled LCD glass and CRT often landfilled solar is recycled	PV panels are separate collected and receive treatment to recover Al, glass and silver, Si ends up in residue for waste incineration or landfill	this layer is either landfilled with residues from PV panel recycling or ends up in recycling fractions without in and Ga recovery
(Partially) existing or potential EoL treatment scenario with CRM recovery	external cables are separated prior shredding, cable scrap undergoes a dedicated treatment with liberation, separation of insulation by density separation, and purification of liberated metals with magnetic separation, purified Cu with 95% purity goes to Cu remelting (Lohb & Espinosa, 2021)	cables and wiring are separated prior shredding or end up in Cu rich fraction for Cu remelting or secondary Cu refining - depending on quality (Lohb & Espinosa, 2021)	coils are separated prior shredding, or hand separated from magnetic fraction, separated coils can be shredded and separated into a magnetic Fe fraction and Cu, the latter goes to Cu remelting or secondary Cu refining - depending on quality	selective removal of LED chips and subsequent thermal and hydrometallurgical treatment (Kebenshauer, 2017b)	enrichment of REE possible with selective removal of LED chips and subsequent treatment, potentially Eu and Y can be hydrolysed with Ga recovery from LED (Bhat et al., 2016)	FLs are collected separately, phosphor powder needs to be removed and is separated due to its Hg content, Eu and Y can be recovered in a subsequent hydrometallurgical or combined pyro-hydrometallurgical process (Dhawan & Tanwar, 2022; European Commission, 2016; Niu et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2013; Figueiredo et al., 2025)	unlikely scenario, Sc is not recovered from metal halide lamps (Botelho et al., 2021; SCREEN CRM fact sheets, 2023)	sorting of plastics according to bromine content into bromine flame retardant (BFR)-containing and BFR-free plastic or alternatively density separation, plastic fraction with BFR can be chemically treated, there are different chemical recycling methods for Sb (Massoli et al., 2019; Gaudin et al., 2025; Spooner, 2025)	selective removal of Al parts from the devices and separate collection after the first removal step or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation (sink/float separation, XRT, LIBS, XRF) from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze, sorted scrap further separated into 5000 and 6000 series Al scrap with LIBS allowing functional Mg recovery and preventing demagging (Diaz-Romero et al., 2023; Park et al., 2021)	selective removal of Al parts from the devices and separate collection after the first removal step or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation (sink/float separation, XRT, LIBS, XRF) from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze, sorted scrap further separated into 5000 and 6000 series Al scrap with LIBS allowing functional Mg recovery and preventing demagging (Diaz-Romero et al., 2023; Park et al., 2021)	selective removal of Al parts from the devices and separate collection after the first removal step or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation (sink/float separation, XRT, LIBS, XRF) from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze, sorted scrap further separated into 5000 and 6000 series Al scrap with LIBS allowing functional Mg recovery and preventing demagging (Diaz-Romero et al., 2023; Park et al., 2021)	removal of magnesium alloy parts from the devices and separate collection followed by remelting or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze and Al alloys, sorted scrap may need removal of coating, remelting of Mg, if quality requires including refining (Wang et al., 2024)	antimony-containing glass is recycled in specialized facilities as antimony can lead to unwanted emissions and lower quality in standard recycling systems for glass (Solar Waste Solutions, n.d.)	PV panels are separate collected and receive treatment to recover Al, glass and silver, Si fraction is separated and purified after pyrolytic separation (Prest & Smith, 2024)	CIGS PV panels are collected separately, the layers in the CIGS PV panels are separated with mechanical or thermal processing followed by a hydrometallurgical or pyrometallurgical process to recover Ga (European Commission, 2016; X. Li et al., 2023)
Nb. Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?														
5.4 Recycling conflicts with hazardous substances	Is there a recycling conflict with hazardous substances? Are there hazardous substances in the respective application/waste flow? Will there be hazardous substances liberated during the recovery process? Can the hazardous substances be contained adequately?														
5.5 Environmental impacts	What are the environmental impacts of the 2CRM in comparison with the primary CRM? Is there any implemented/standardized calculation pathway for environmental impact assessment?														
6.1 Recovery targets	Are there material or element specific recovery targets?														
6.2 Removal requirements	Are there any removal requirements related to the CRM containing application?														
6.3 Legal incentives	Are there any legal incentives for the recovery of the CRM such as special facilities in application, permission or registration processes?														
6.4 End-of-waste criteria	Are there established end-of-waste criteria for 2CRM?														

target CRM	Cu	Cu	Cu	Ga	Eu, Y	Eu, Y	Sc	Sb	Al	Al	Mg	Mg	Sb	Si	Ga
application/waste flow	external cables	internal cables and wiring	coils in motors	LEDs for general lighting and background illumination	LEDs for general lighting and background illumination	phosphor powder in fluorescent lamps (FL for general lighting and background illumination (CFLs))	arc tube in metal halide lamps in camera or industrial and street lighting	flame retardant in plastic casing	heat sinks in various applications	Al alloys in casing, frame, chassis	alloying element in Al alloys in casing, frame, chassis	Mg alloys - mostly in casing	glass (e.g. LCD, CRT, solar)	silicon PV cells	thin layer in CIGS PV cells
End treatment scenario without CRM recovery	mechanical treatment of devices, cables end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete liberation and separation. Cu ends up in landfill, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	mechanical treatment of devices, cables end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete liberation and separation. Cu ends up in landfill, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	mechanical treatment of devices, coils end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete separation. Cu ends up in landfill, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	fate of LED relevant, can either end up in plastics fraction or metal fraction. Ga ends up in bottom ash after incineration or smelter slag	fate of LED relevant, can either end up in plastics fraction or metal fraction. Eu and Y end up in bottom ash after incineration or smelter slag	due to their mercury content FLs need to be collected and treated separately, phosphor powder needs to be removed and is separated due to its Hg content. Mg is recovered through vaporization. Eu and Y are not recovered	due to their mercury content metal halide lamps need to be collected and treated separately. Hg is recovered through vaporization. Sc is not recovered	incineration or energy recovery of plastic parts, flame retardants often volatilize or remain in residues/ Fly ash	heat sinks mounted to components do not get separated and are shredded without complete liberation. Al alloys end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fractions	casing, frame, chassis do not get separated, entire device gets shredded without complete liberation. Al alloys end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fractions	Mg can also be an impurity in Al alloys after remelting if not functionally recycled or removed through demagging	Casing, frame, chassis do not get separated, entire device is shredded with or without complete liberation. Mg alloys end up in Al fraction. Mg oxidizes easily at high temperatures, especially when not protected. MgO ends up in slag	antimony-containing glass is separated, but not recycled LCD glass and CRT often landfilled solar is recycled	PV panels are separate collected and receive treatment to recover Al glass and silver. Si ends up in residue for waste incineration or landfill	this layer is either landfilled with residues from PV panel recycling or ends up in recycling fractions without an and Ga recovery
Partially/ existing or potential End treatment scenario with CRM recovery	external cables are separated prior shredding, cable scrap undergoes a dedicated treatment with liberation, separation of insulation by density separation, and purification of liberated metals with magnetic separation, purified Cu with 95% purity goes to Cu remelting (Lobbi & Espinosa, 2021)	cables and wiring are separated prior shredding or end up in Cu-rich fraction for Cu remelting or secondary Cu refining - depending on quality (Lobbi & Espinosa, 2021)	coils are separated prior shredding, or hand separated from magnetic fraction, separated into a magnetic Fe fraction and Cu, the latter goes to Cu remelting or secondary Cu refining - depending on quality	selective removal of LED chips and subsequent thermal and hydrometallurgical treatment (Kobierska, 2017b)	enrichment of REE possible with selective removal of LED chips and subsequent treatment, potentially Eu and Y can be produced with Ga recovery from LED (Butler et al., 2016)	FLs are collected separately, phosphor powder needs to be removed and is separated due to its Hg content. Eu and Y can be recovered in a subsequent hydrometallurgical or combined pyro-hydrometallurgical process (Dhawan & Tarwar, 2022; European Commission, 2016; Niu et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2013; Figueiredo et al., 2025)	unlikely scenario, Sc is not recovered from metal halide lamps (Botelho et al., 2021; SCREEN CRM's fact sheets, 2023).	sorting of plastics according to bromine content into bromine flame retardant (BFR)-containing and BFR-free plastics or alternatively density separation, plastic fraction with BFR can be chemically treated, there are different chemical recycling methods for Sb (Almassi et al., 2019; Goudin et al., 2025; Spoonen, 2025)	selective removal of Al parts from the devices and separate collection after the first removal step or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation (link/float separation, XRT, LIBS, XRF) from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze, sorted scrap for remelting of Al (Diaz-Romero et al., 2023; Park et al., 2021)	selective removal of Al parts from the devices and separate collection after the first removal step or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation (link/float separation, XRT, LIBS, XRF) from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze, sorted scrap for remelting of Al (Diaz-Romero et al., 2023; Park et al., 2021)	selective removal of Al parts from the devices and separate collection after the first removal step or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation (link/float separation, XRT, LIBS, XRF) from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze, sorted scrap further separated into 5000 and 6000 series Al scrap with LIBS allowing functional Mg recovery and preventing demagging (Diaz-Romero et al., 2023; Park et al., 2021)	removal of magnesium alloy parts from the devices and separate collection followed by remelting or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze and Al alloys, sorted scrap may need removal of coating, remelting of Mg, if quality requires allowing refining (Wang et al., 2024)	antimony-containing glass is recycled in specialized facilities as antimony can lead to unwanted emissions and lower quality in standard recycling systems for glass (Solar Waste Solutions, n.d.)	PV panels are separate collected and receive treatment to recover Al glass and silver. Si fraction is separated and purified after pyrolytic separation (Preet & Smith, 2024)	CIGS PV panels are collected separately, the layers in the CIGS PV panels are separated with mechanical or thermal processing followed by a hydrometallurgical or pyrometallurgical process to recover Ga (European Commission, 2016; X. Li et al., 2023)

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target CRM application/waste flow	Cu external cables	Cu internal cables and wiring	Cu coils in motors	Ga LEDs for general lighting and background illumination	Eu, Y LEDs for general lighting and background illumination	Eu, Y LEDs for general lighting and background illumination	Sc phosphor powder in fluorescent lamps (FLA) for general lighting and background illumination (CCFL)	Sb arc tube in metal halide lamps in camera or industrial and street lighting	Sb flame retardant in plastic casing	Al heat sinks in various applications	Al Al alloys in casing, frame, chassis	Mg alloying element in Al alloys in casing, frame, chassis	Mg Mg alloys - mostly in casing	Sb glass (e.g. LCD, CRT, solar)	Si silicon PV cells	Ga thin layer in CIGS PV cells
EoL treatment scenario without CRM recovery	mechanical treatment of devices, cables end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete liberation and separation, Cu ends up in landfills, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	mechanical treatment of devices, cables and wiring end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete liberation and separation, Cu ends up in landfills, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	mechanical treatment of devices, coils end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete separation, Cu ends up in landfills, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al induction motors may go directly to steel recycling where Cu is lost as impurity	fate of LED relevant, can either end up in plastics fraction or metal fraction, Ga ends up in bottom ash after incineration or smelter slag	fate of LED relevant, can either end up in plastics fraction or metal fraction, Eu and Y end up in bottom ash after incineration or smelter slag	fate of LED relevant, can either end up in plastics fraction or metal fraction, Eu and Y end up in bottom ash after incineration or smelter slag	due to their mercury content FLA need to be collected and treated separately, phosphor powder needs to be removed and is separated due to its Hg content, Mg is recovered through vaporization, Eu and Y are not recovered	due to their mercury content metal halide lamps need to be collected and treated separately, Mg is recovered through vaporization, Sc is not recovered	incineration or energy recovery of plastic parts, flame retardants often volatilize or remain in residues/fly ash	heat sinks mounted to components do not get separated and are shredded without complete liberation, Al alloys end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fractions	casing, frame, chassis do not get separated, entire device gets shredded without complete liberation, Al alloys end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fractions	mechanical treatment of devices, Al alloys end up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete separation	Casing, frame, chassis do not get separated, entire device is shredded with or without complete liberation, Mg alloys end up in Al fraction, Mg oxidizes easily at high temperatures, especially when not protected, MgO ends up in slags	antimony-containing glass is separated, but not recycled LCD glass and CRT often landfilled solar is recycled	PV panels are separate collected and receive treatment to recover Al glass and silver, Si ends up in residue for waste incineration or landfill	this layer is either landfilled with residues from PV panel recycling or ends up in recycling fractions without In and Ga recovery
(Partially) existing or potential EoL treatment scenario with CRM recovery	external cables are separated prior shredding, cable scrap undergoes a dedicated treatment with liberation, separation of insulation by density separation, and purification of liberated metals with magnetic separation, purified Cu with 95% purity goes to Cu remelting (Lohb & Espinosa, 2021)	cables and wiring are separated prior shredding or end up in Cu rich fraction for Cu remelting or secondary Cu refining - depending on quality (Lohb & Espinosa, 2021)	coils are separated prior shredding, or hand separated from magnetic fraction, separated coils can be shredded and separated into a magnetic Fe fraction and Cu, the latter goes to Cu remelting or secondary Cu refining - depending on quality	selective removal of LED chips and subsequent thermal and hydrometallurgical treatment (Leberschauer, 2017b)	enrichment of REE possible with selective removal of LED chips and subsequent treatment, potentially Eu and Y can be by-product with Ga recovery from LED (Bhat et al., 2016)	FLAs are collected separately, phosphor powder needs to be removed and is separated due to its Hg content, Eu and Y can be recovered in a subsequent hydrometallurgical or combined pyro-hydrometallurgical process (Dhawan & Tanwar, 2022; European Commission, 2016; Niu et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2013; Figueiredo et al., 2025)	FLAs are collected separately, phosphor powder needs to be removed and is separated due to its Hg content, Eu and Y can be recovered in a subsequent hydrometallurgical or combined pyro-hydrometallurgical process (Dhawan & Tanwar, 2022; European Commission, 2016; Niu et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2013; Figueiredo et al., 2025)	unlikely scenario, Sc is not recovered from metal halide lamps (Botelho et al., 2021; SCREEN CRMs fact sheets, 2023).	sorting of plastics according to bromine content into bromine flame retardant (BFR)-containing and BFR-free plastics or alternatively density separation, plastic fraction with BFR can be chemically treated, there are different chemical recycling methods for Sb (Almassol et al., 2019; Gaudin et al., 2025; Spooner, 2025)	selective removal of Al parts from the devices and separate collection after the first removal step or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation (sink/float separation, XRT, LIBS, XRF) from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze, sorted scrap for remelting of Al (Diaz-Romero et al., 2023; Park et al., 2021)	selective removal of Al parts from the devices and separate collection after the first removal step or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation (sink/float separation, XRT, LIBS, XRF) from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze, sorted scrap for remelting of Al (Diaz-Romero et al., 2023; Park et al., 2021)	selective removal of Al parts from the devices and separate collection after the first removal step or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation (sink/float separation, XRT, LIBS, XRF) from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze, sorted scrap for remelting of Al (Diaz-Romero et al., 2023; Park et al., 2021)	removal of magnesium alloy parts from the devices and separate collection followed by remelting or liberation during mechanical treatment of the devices and eddy current with further separation from other non-ferrous impurities such as Cu, brass, or bronze and Al alloys, sorted scrap may need removal of coating, remelting (Wang et al., 2024)	antimony-containing glass is recycled in specialized facilities as antimony can lead to unwanted emissions and lower quality in standard recycling systems for glass (Solar Waste Solutions, n.d.)	PV panels are separate collected and receive treatment to recover Al glass and silver, Si fraction is separated and purified after pyrolytic separation (Preet & Smith, 2024)	CIGS PV panels are collected separately, the layers in the CIGS PV panels are separated with mechanical or thermal processing followed by a hydrometallurgical or pyrometallurgical process to recover Ga (European Commission, 2016; X. Li et al., 2023)
Nb. Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?															

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 TOMRA Recycling, 2025
 U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 2015
 Uberschauer & Rotter, 2015
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Regulation (EC) 1272/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on classification, labelling, and packaging of substances and mixtures

Commission Regulation (EU) No 715/2013 of 25 July 2013 establishing criteria determining when copper scrap ceases to be waste under Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council

Regulation (EU) 2024/252 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 April 2024 establishing a framework for ensuring a secure and sustainable supply of critical raw materials and amending Regulations (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/772 and (EU) 2019/1020

Regulation (EU) 2024/1781 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 June 2024 establishing a framework for the setting of eco-design requirements for sustainable products, amending Directive (EU) 2020/1828 and Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 and repealing Directive 2009/225/EC

Commission Regulation (EU) No 1179/2012 of 10 December 2012 establishing criteria determining when glass cullet ceases to be waste under Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council

Council Regulation (EU) No 333/2011 of 31 March 2011 establishing criteria determining when certain types of scrap metal cease to be waste under Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council

Regulation (EU) 2019/1021 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on persistent organic pollutants (recast)

Directive 2012/19/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) (recast)

- Abbreviations used
- ATO Antimony trioxide
 - BFR Brominated flame retardant
 - CCFL Cold Cathode Fluorescent Lamp
 - CIGS Cu-Indium-Gallium-Selenide
 - CRM Critical Raw Material
 - CRT Cathode Ray Tube
 - DPP Digital Product Passport
 - EoL End-of-life
 - EU European Union
 - FL Fluorescent Lamp
 - HDD Hard Disk Drive
 - LED Liquid-crystal display
 - LED Light-emitting diode
 - LIBS Laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy
 - NIR Near-infrared
 - PCB Printed Circuit Board
 - REE Rare Earth Elements
 - TRL Technology Readiness Level
 - XRF X-ray fluorescence
 - XRT X-ray transmission